

Table 2. Curative efficacy of certain chemicals for rice seed discoloration.^a Bangkok, Thailand.

Treatment	Dose (a.i./ha)	Total seeds per panicle	Healthy seeds per panicle	Dirty seeds per panicle	Empty seeds per panicle
Control	0	120.81 a	56.45 a	54.26 a	10.10 a
Copper oxychloride	0.5 kg	94.33 a	48.61 a	36.95 a	8.77 a
MBC + mancozeb	0.75 kg	128.18 a	69.71 a	49.13 a	9.34 a
Mancozeb	0.75 kg	94.13 a	51.35 a	34.41 a	8.37 a
Edifenphos	0.5 liter	103.93 a	52.45 a	42.70 a	8.18 a
Polyoxin Z	1.5 kg	95.51 a	54.01 a	34.33 a	7.17 a
Sisthane	1 liter	99.13 a	58.71 a	32.01 a	8.41 a
Carboxin	1.75 liters	106.66 a	69.48 a	25.98 a	11.20 a
CV		15.0%	26.56%	38.0%	48.4%

^a Means followed by the same letter do not differ significantly at the 5% level.

Plants treated with Polyoxin Z gave the highest number of healthy seeds (97.95) per panicle, followed by Sisthane with 90.61, and edifenphos with 76.91. Plants treated with copper oxychloride

had the lowest number of healthy seeds (57.61) per panicle, which was lower than that from the control plot. Copper oxychloride, which caused the highest number of dirty seeds (79.18) per pani-

cle, may be toxic to the panicle (Table 1).

No fungicide showed ability to cure the disease or decrease damage (Table 2). ■

Pest management and control INSECTS

Dimorphopterus similis Slater (Heteroptera: Lygaeidae: Blissinae), a new rice pest from Nigeria

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During a recent survey of rice pests in Sokoto State, Nigeria, a large population of *Dimorphopterus similis* was encountered in rice stubble after harvest. The presence of this species in large numbers (av: 16 adult *D. similis* /hill) and complete failure of crops (yield about 50 kg/ha, or 3% of the 1974 average productivity for Africa) indicate that *D. similis* may become a major rice pest in Nigeria, and elsewhere.

Six species of Blissinae have been reported on rice *Oryza sativa*: *Blissus richardsoni* Drake from Cuba (Bruner et al 1945), *B. insularis* Barber from St. Croix (Wolcott 1936), *Ischnodemus congoensis* Slater from S. Rhodesia (Slater 1964a); *I. diplachne* Slater and Harrington from S. Rhodesia (now Zimbabwe) (Slater and Harrington 1970); *I. perplexus* Slater and Harrington from Senegal (Slater and Harrington 1970); and *Cavelerius excavatus* (Distant) from India (Fletcher 1921). This report, therefore, brings the

number found on rice to seven. It is also the first report of a species of *Dimorphopterus* with economic potential. This is interesting because *Dimorphopterus* is evidently the Old World ecological equivalent of the western hemisphere's *Blissus*, several species of which have economic importance (Hamid and Slater 1979). In view of the above and to facilitate further studies, we have summarized the present knowledge about *D. similis*.

This species originally was described from a single female from South Africa. It was next reported from Senegal and Nigeria. Host plants previously were unknown, although the specimens reported from Nigeria were collected on *Hyparrhenia involucreata* Stapf. (Gramineae). All reports from Africa, including the present one, were from grassland regions.

D. similis is one of 35 species presently included in the genus *Dimorphopterus*. These are distributed mainly in the Ethiopian (16), Oriental (10), and Palearctic (7) regions, but two species also extend into Australia.

The taxonomic status of a number of species of *Dimorphopterus*, including *D. similis*, is not satisfactorily established. This species is closely related to *D. nubicus*, *D. brachypterus*, and *D. graminum*, all reported from Nigeria. It

is desirable to study *D. similis* and its closest taxa to more satisfactorily establish their relationship. ■

Effect of potash levels on the incidence of rice whorl maggot

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Earlier work on the correlation between potash level and the occurrence of the rice whorl maggot showed that up to 135 kg potassium/ha had no effect on the maggot.

A trial conducted during the 1978-79 samba season (Jul-Aug to Nov-Dec) at PES, Tirur, used higher levels of K than

Effect of potash levels on whorl maggot damage. 1978-79 samba season, Tirur, Tamil Nadu, India.

K (kg/ha)	Damaged tillers ^a (%) 30 DT ^b
0	13.9 a
25	14.8 a
50	14.1 a
75	14.2 a
100	16.6 ab
125	16.3 ab
150	18.1 ab
175	20.8 b
200	24.2 b
CD	5R

^a Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^b Days after transplanting.

those tested earlier. The trial was laid out with rice variety IR8 and 9 levels of potash: 0, 25, 50, 75, 100, 125, 150, 175, and 200 kg K/ha. Potash was applied basally at the time of planting and no insecticide was used. Whorl maggot infestation was assessed 30 days after

transplanting on the basis of percentage of damaged tillers.

The results revealed that whorl maggot damage increased only at the two highest rates of potash (see table). Plants with 175 or 200 kg K/ha had significantly higher whorl maggot dam-

age than those with 0-75 kg K/ha. But the grain yield differences were not statistically significant.

The local fertilizer recommendation is only 50 kg K/ha. Potash application at that level is not expected to increase whorl maggot damage in rice. ■

Control of daphnids in blue-green algae multiplication plots

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The main problem in field multiplication plots is the damage caused by daphnids that live on the soil surface and form small mud tunnels. Usually, daphnids lie horizontally on the soil surface. When conditions are favorable, the population buildup is so heavy that space becomes unavailable. The daphnids then stick one end of their nests in the soil substrate in a standing water column. If the blue-green algae (BGA) multiplication site is left unprotected, the dense mass of BGA growing on the water surface will vanish within a couple of days because of the severity of damage caused by daphnids.

To develop a suitable control measure, three randomized replicated trials during 1979 kuruvai tested seven granular insecticides in three concentrations (normal, double, triple doses). Because BGA already were established in the field, no BGA seed material was applied to the experimental plots. P₂O₅ in the form of superphosphate was applied uniformly to supply 32 kg/ha to all plots as a nutrient for algal activity. The granular insecticides were applied as per treatment. Water depth was maintained permanently at 10 cm. On the 10th day, the BGA mass floating on the water surface was collected separately for each treatment. It was spread on a threshing floor and allowed to dry in the sun. The dried algal flakes were collected and weighed.

The results indicated that carbofuran at double dose, and quinalphos, mephosfolan and diazinon at normal doses can be used to control daphnids in BGA multiplication units. ■

Effect of granular insecticides on BGA seed material in multiplication plots. Aduthurai, India.

Insecticide and formulation	Normal rate (kg a.i./ha)	BGA seed material (kg/10 m ²)		
		Normal dose	Double dose	Triple dose
Carbofuran 3% G	0.6	6.1	9.0	8.9
Carbaryl 4% G	0.8	5.0	7.3	5.8
B.H.C. 6.5% G	1.3	3.5	5.7	6.7
Quinalphos 5% G	0.6	8.8	9.1	9.0
Mephosfolan 5% G	0.5	8.6	9.1	7.3
Phorate 10% G	1.3	5.0	6.7	8.0
Diazinon 10% G	1.0	8.5	8.9	9.0
Control		0.8	0.9	0.6
C.D. (P= 0.05%)		1.2	1.6	1.1

Insecticides sprayed on brown planthopper eggs

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Timing insecticide applications for brown planthopper (BPH) control is difficult because at any one time a field population will be composed of eggs, nymphs, and adults. To reduce insecticide cost an insecticide that has efficacy against all stages is desirable. We tested for ovicidal activity insecticides that showed activity against BPH adults. We report on the ovicidal activity of several coded and commercial insecticides.

Two gravid female BPH in each cage oviposited for 24 hours on 30-day-old TN1 plants. After oviposition, the females were removed and the potted plants sprayed with 6.25 ml of insecticidal solution per pot. Hatched nymphs were counted daily and removed until hatching terminated. Unhatched eggs were counted after the plants were dissected.

Among the 12 insecticides used, 6 had high ovicidal activity: UC 54229, FMC 35001, UC SF-1, UC 27867, carbaryl, and azinphos-ethyl (see table). Propoxur, decamethrin, and NNI-750 had low activity. Diazinon, BHC, and chlorpyrifos had no effect. UC 54229, UC SF-1, and UC 27867 are coded car-

Ovicidal activity of foliar sprayed insecticides on *N. lugens* eggs. IIRI greenhouse, 1980.

Common name	Insecticides ^a		Hatched eggs (%) ^b
	Trade name	Formulation	
UC 54229		100% Tech.	0.7 a
FMC 35001	Marshall	20% EC	1.1 a
UC SF-1		40% F	2.7 a
UC 27867		50% WP	2.9 a
Carbaryl	Sevin	85% WP	2.8 a
Azinphos-ethyl	Gusathion A	40% EC	3.9 a
Propoxur	Unden	20% EC	77.6 b
Decamethrin	Decis	2.5% EC	78.1 b
NNI-750		25% WP	80.4 b
Diazinon	Basudin	20% EC	94.0 c
BHC	Lindane	26% WP	96.6 c
Chlorpyrifos	Lorsban	40% EC	96.0 c
Control			97.5 c

^aSprayed at the rate of 0.075% concentration (0.75 kg a.i./ha at a spray volume of 1,000 liters/ha). EC= emulsifiable concentrate, WP = wettable powder, Tech. = technical formulation. ^bAv of 4 replications. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.